

***Paraprososthenia liyuntongi*, a new replacement name for *Paraprososthenia lijiangensis* Y.-T. Li, 1988 (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoda: Pomatiopsidae)**

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Abstract. *Paraprososthenia liyuntongi* **nom. nov.** is proposed to replace *Paraprososthenia lijiangensis* Y.-T. Li, 1988, from the Sheshan Formation (Lower or Middle Pleistocene) in the Lijiang Basin, western Yunnan, China.

Key words. new name, *Paraprososthenia lijiangensis*, Yunnan, China, taxon

Paraprososthenia liyuntongi* **nom. nov.*

李氏川蜷 (Pinyin: lǐ shì chuān quán)

Paraprososthenia lijiangensis Y.-T. Li, 1988: 162, pl. 2, figs 11–15. (preoccupied by Y.-Y. Liu, Y.-X. Wang & W.-Z. Zhang, 1980: 358, figs I-2, II-1)

Etymology. The species is named after the original author of the taxa, Yun-Tong Li, a Chinese paleontologist tragically died in a traffic accident on 5 December 1987 while conducting geological fieldwork in Xichang, Sichuan, China (Editorial, 1988).

Description. see Li (1988).

Notes. Li (1988) described a new pomatiopsid fossil species, *Paraprososthenia lijiangensis* Y.-T. Li, 1988, from the Sheshan Formation (Lower or Middle Pleistocene) in the Lijiang Basin, western Yunnan, China. However, this name is preoccupied by *Paraprososthenia lijiangensis* Y.-Y. Liu, Y.-X. Wang & W.-Z. Zhang, 1980, an extant species likewise recorded from Lijiang, Yunnan. Therefore, the junior objective homonym must be replaced.

References

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李氏川蜷是丽江川蜷的新名称 (腹足纲: 新进腹足亚纲: 盖螺科)

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摘 要

来自云南省西部丽江盆地蛇山组的盖螺科的一个川蜷属化石种, 被重新命名为李氏川蜷。原名称与同样原产云南丽江的现生的一种川蜷同名。

关键词: 新名称, 丽江川蜷, 云南, 中国, 分类单元